

Autonomous Robot Choreography for Music Performance Augmentation

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Abstract—Dance choreography is the kinematic interpretation of a soundtrack, which translates the music into rhythmic and synchronized movements. The dance makes the sounds visible through body language and the performer’s movements, enhancing and augmenting the audience’s experience. This work proposes an approach to augment artistic performance by music-driven choreographies tailored for manipulators autonomously¹.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, people’s ideas of robots changed, moving from caged manipulators in factories towards robots that share spaces with humans and support them in their daily activities. Moreover, the choreographies of the physicist and dancer Merritt Moore² or of pro dancer Roberto Bolle³, demonstrated that the robots have captivated the entertainment world encouraging artists to bring robots with them on stage to create augmented performance. In recent years, thanks to the work of researchers and companies [1]–[3], the application field of robots has become wider, including several unconventional disciplines such as art and show business. Following this trend of interest, we propose a novel method aimed at creating an augmented music experience through robot choreography. The robot, like a human dancer, hears the melody, understands the rhythms, and choreographs, also in real-time, movements following the audio track decomposed in the signals of the ensemble instruments. In this scenario, musicians and manipulators represent two independent entities on the stage, engaging in a dialogue based on sounds and movements augmenting the audience experience.

II. METHODS

In the proposed work we present a novel autonomous strategy to augment human musical performances by involving robots on the same stage stepped by a singer or a band. The proposed method generates rhythmic robot movements starting from audio tracks, also played in live, augmenting the artistic expressiveness. To provide synchronous movements of the robot with the played song, the proposed method fosters direction change of the robot movement following the tempo of the

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²Merritt + Robot Dance: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uSOHc3ODLzU>

³Danza con Me: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XH8C0i51ezk>

Fig. 1: Music-driven approach for autonomously choreographing robot movements.

audio track. The main challenge to take of consists of enabling several degrees of freedom (DoFs) of a robot using only one acoustic signal preserving the expressiveness of the music track. To face this we, take inspiration from the work of Cuan *et al.* presented in [4], in which the matching of robot DoFs and the audio track is performed splitting the latter into the audio tracks of each consisting instrument. In detail, as depicted in Fig. 1, we propose a three-step mapping policy consisting of *i*) Principal Components Analysis of Robot Movements, to define the basis of robot joint posture, *ii*) Music Track Processing, the audio sources are sub-sampled and elaborated to be used for triggering the movements of the robots, and *iii*) In Robot Choreography Generation, the processed audio signals are projected towards the PC space of the robot computing time-to-time its movements.

A. Principal Components Analysis of Robot Movements

Performing principal component analysis, the original data space of robot movement is linearly transformed into a rotated version of itself, aligning its axes with the directions of highest variance. This approach fosters the rooting of the robot’s movements into the space of its commonly attained postures. It provides an effective transformation that allows the map of N DoFs of audio sources onto the robot joint space with cardinality equal to M , having $M \geq N$. Then, starting from the joint postures of a robot at time instant t , denoted as $\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^M$ and defined as the set of M joint angle values $\theta_m(t) \in \mathbb{R}$, a singular value decomposition of these is performed offline to evaluate their principal components $z(t)$ as $\theta(t) = \Lambda z(t)$, where $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$ is the transformation matrix composed of the eigenvectors of $\theta(t)^T \theta(t)$, $\forall t \in \{0, t_r\}$ and t_r is equal to the temporal duration of the robot movements. Using the transformation matrix, $\tilde{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$, composed of only first N eigenvectors of $\theta^T \theta$, we obtain that the robot postures are

approximated as follows: $\theta(t) \approx \tilde{\Lambda}\tilde{z}(t)$, with $\tilde{z}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the set of first N PCs of robot movements. In this way, we define a transformation matrix that maps a reduced number of PCs onto a well approximated space of joints, reducing the number of robot independent movements.

B. Music Track Processing

To choreograph robot movement starting from an already recorded song, the audio tracks can be split off-line into their consisting instrument audio signals exploiting well-known algorithms based on filtering or machine learning [5]. For live shows, each instrument could be separately and directly acquired to be processed and mapped in real time.

In this context, time-dependent signal provided from each audio source (the i -th of N instruments) is denoted with $s_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}$, while the whole song is indicated with $S(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. The acquisition of these signals commonly involves state-of-the-art systems capable of high-frequency sampling, having a significantly higher frequency compared to the tempo T of the song. To ensure synchronous timing for robot motion, the first step of audio processing involves down-sampling the audio tracks according to the song tempo, gathering a sample at the pace of $S(t)$. To perform this, we consider an additional instrument used to mark the tempo, the metronome. The down-sampled signals are sorted to be successively mapped onto the PCs of the robot. The sorting is performed following the descending ordering of the contribution of each i -th instrument, and collected in $\tilde{s}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^M$.

C. Robot Choreography Generation

The last step of the proposed methods involves the processed audio signals within the PC space of the robot as references to compute its joint postures, enabling the robot to autonomously execute synchronous and rhythmic choreography. A PC-like signal $\zeta(t)$ from audio sources is calculated rescaling the instrument tracks to fit the amplitudes of the robot PCs: $\zeta(t) = K\tilde{s}(t)$, where K is the scale factor equal to the ratio between the maximum value reached by PCs of the robot and the line level of audio sources $s_{u,dB} \in \mathbb{R}$: In this way, we evaluate the references for the robot evaluated in its PC space. To compute the corresponding trajectories in the joint space, ζ is mapped onto the joint space of the robot through the linear transformation $\tilde{\Lambda}$: $\theta_d(t) = \tilde{\Lambda}\zeta(t)$. This yields the desired posture $\theta_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ for the robot dance for each beat of the song. In the end, between two beats $(k-1)T$ and kT the zero-value samples are replaced by exploiting a third order interpolation.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

One hundred choreographies originated by combining two datasets comprising robot movements and royalty-free music tracks. The first dataset is an ad-hoc collection of ten joint postures obtained from an existing dataset presented in [6], while the music dataset includes ten melodies selected from a larger pool publicly available in the Pixabay repository (Canva Inc., AU), covering a wide range of genres, tempos, and rhythms. Additionally, these two datasets are then combined

Fig. 2: Results of the statistical analysis about levels of incoherence between θ and θ_d with any melodies S .

using the proposed method to generate one hundred choreographies tailored for a virtual mock-up exploiting the web service Splitter AI to obtain instrumental audio sources.

IV. VALIDATION

To observe the level of coherence between the obtained robot choreographies and the melody, we exploited the dynamic wrapping of the $S(t)$ audio signals, S with the amplitude maps of movements of all joints θ_d . The resulting maps are used to measure the Euclidean distance $d_e(S, \Theta_d)$, of robot joint movements with respect to the melody. Then, a comprehensive statistical analysis (see Fig. 2) was performed to assess the significance of enhancements in coherence between melodies and the robot movements before and after the method application. The qualitative and quantitative outcomes confirmed that the proposed method effectively transforms a repetitive movement of an industrial nature into a dance choreography with an effective improvement of consistency with the background melody, thus increasing the musical artistic performance through the dance of a robot.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we propose a new approach to autonomously augment musical performances by robot choreographies. In future work, audience and artist opinions about the created choreographies will be collected and analyzed.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Rogel, R. Savery, N. Yang, and G. Weinberg, "Robogroove: Creating fluid motion for dancing robotic arms," in *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Movement and Computing*, 2022, pp. 1–9.
- [2] G. Saviano, A. Villani, and D. Prattichizzo, "A pca-based method to map aesthetic movements from dancer to robotic arm," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Robotics and Its Social Impacts (ARSO)*, 2023, pp. 71–77.
- [3] —, "From cage to stage: Mapping human dance movements onto industrial robotic arm motion," in *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Movement and Computing*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [4] C. Cuan, E. Fisher, A. Okamura, and T. Engbersen, "Music mode: Transforming robot movement into music increases likability and perceived intelligence," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.02632*, 2023.
- [5] Y. Luo and J. Yu, "Music source separation with band-split rnn," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 2023.
- [6] A. S. Polydoros and L. Nalpantidis, "A reservoir computing approach for learning forward dynamics of industrial manipulators," in *2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2016, pp. 612–618.